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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To effectively carry out the activities planned as part of the Living Lab (LL) process, an effective methodology is required. In the ACCEPT project, the hybrid methodology was implemented to ensure LL activities required for the co-creation of the technological development and the integration of technologies in the community with all stakeholders and citizens at pilot locations. Following the first iteration of the hybrid approach which produced the first engagement roadmap (reported in D3.1), a second iteration of the engagement roadmap has been created. This updated engagement roadmap is a result of interviews with the project and technical leaders (top-down) and work package and pilot leaders (bottom-up). From the project onset to M12, five engagements are ongoing or completed (the five engagements refer broadly to activities such as introducing ACCEPT to the community as one engagement, in practice this constitutes many engagements across the 4 pilot sites). A further 22 engagements are planned for the remainder of the project lifespan, 12 of which will occur in the period of M13-M24.

The engagements carried out thus far have been considered in two channels, (1) services and solutions, such as use case and business case development in WP2 and technical development in WP4 and (2) pilot related engagements that address contextual requirements at pilot sites as well as pilot-specific goals and key stakeholders in the framework of the ACCEPT project. Engagements undertaken in the context of services and solutions include surveys carried out with external stakeholders to gauge the interest in ACCEPT services, internal assessment of potential business models and service-level agreements (SLA contracts), and ex-ante surveys aimed at the recruitment of pilot participants conducted as part of WP6. From these activities, a total of 353 stakeholders have been engaged across the 4 pilot locations, see Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the number of stakeholders reached through use case development and engagement activities

Pilot	Number of responses to concept survey	Number of responses to the ex-ante survey
Greece	39	61
Spain	44	55
Switzerland	28	64
Netherlands	22	40
TOTAL	133	220

Several activities have also been undertaken as part of the pilot site engagements. Firstly, internal engagements took place as part of WP3 to assess the pilot locations in terms of stakeholder mapping, goal definition and local barriers and drivers. This activity was initially planned as a physical site visit to the pilot locations, however, due to Covid-19 restrictions, this activity was carried out through remote channels such as interviews and telcos with pilot representatives. In addition to the assessment under the scope of WP3, many activities were carried out by the pilot partners aimed at raising awareness of ACCEPT, recruiting pilot participants and gathering initial feedback on the services provided in ACCEPT. Table 2 displays an overview of the number of pilot engagement activities.

Table 2. Summary of the number of pilot engagement activities

Pilot	Number of activities between WP3 leaders and pilot representatives	Number of activities performed by pilot representatives with community
Greece	3	2
Spain	3	2
Switzerland	3	3
Netherlands	3	3
TOTAL	12	10

The engagement activities conducted thus far in the LL process have contributed to the overall KPIs outlined in the grant agreement. Specifically, with regards to the KPIs related to engaging with a minimum number of stakeholders, thus far, 133 of 1000 required for co-creation have been reached and 220 of the 770 required for validation have been reached. With the activities planned in the period of M12-24 targeted at co-creation of the ACCEPT APPs and validation of the consumer personas that will be developed, it is expected the targets for stakeholders to be engaged will be met. With regards to the KPI of developing 10 best practices on energy community creation, despite still being in the early stages of the project, prior to implementation of the testbed and demonstration activities, the first best practice of “Understanding the community and stakeholders” has been defined.

GLOSSARY

DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
SLA	Service-level agreement
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

The primary objective of task 3.1 is to define the engagement roadmap of the Living Lab activities in ACCEPT. At this stage, the framework for planning engagements, including determining key stakeholders, understanding local context and pilot goals and coordinating with consortium members from both the technical and pilot perspective has been implemented. This process has identified engagements required across the project lifespan, several of which have taken place in the first 12 months. The focus of this task is not to provide in-depth details of outcomes of tasks in other work packages, it is to report on the engagements that took place within those work packages and comment on how the engagement impacts the project.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

- Chapter 2 will describe the hybrid approach and its implementation in the first 12 months of the project. The roles and responsibilities of partners in the LL process will be outlined. The resulting engagement roadmap from the hybrid approach will be provided and the LL process will be evaluated.
- Chapter 3 will describe the status of engagements planned to take place in the first 12 months of the project related to services and solutions and solutions developed in the project.
- Chapter 4 will describe the status of engagements related to the pilot sites planned for the first 12 months. This includes activities conducted through WP3 and engagements conducted by pilot partners aimed at introducing ACCEPT to the community and recruiting pilot participants.
- Chapter 5 will evaluate the LL process and discuss the related KPIs outlined in the grant agreement.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Due to the co-creation aspect of the Living Lab process, there are interdependencies with most tasks and work packages within ACCEPT. Any task that requires feedback from internal or external stakeholders will be dependent on task 3.1. This will include the activities of the technological development related to WP2, 4 and 5, and the pre-validation and beta testing in WP6. The LL activities in WP3 are synonymous with the pilot sites and demonstration activities performed in WP7. The impact assessment and preliminary business model analysis will also require input from the framework defined in this task, likely to take place in the later phases of the project. WP9 activities will be closely linked to T3.1 as communication is an important intertwined element of the engagement process.

2. Living lab process

Following the definition of the LL framework in D3.1, the focus of the LL process in T3.1 has turned towards the execution of engagements and the monitoring and updating of the engagement roadmap. In addition, the LL process is continually evaluated to ensure efficiency and effectiveness.

To successfully carry out the engagements in the LL process, a clear understanding of the roles and responsibilities of each partner involved is required. The success of the LL process is highly dependent on the contributions and active involvement of all consortium partners. A division of the roles and responsibilities of partners involved in the LL process was developed and presented in D3.1, and this division holds valid today. Each partner, including LL leader, project and technical coordination, demo leaders and WP leaders continue to have determined roles in LL implementation.

2.1. Living Lab process - the Hybrid Approach

The Hybrid approach utilized for developing the engagement roadmap involves gathering input from both the top-down and bottom-up perspectives to ensure the goals of the ACCEPT project and the goals of the pilot partners are achieved (for more information on the Hybrid approach, refer to D3.1).

The initial implementation of the hybrid approach consisted of developing a top-down timeline with the project and technical coordinators and combining this with information on individual tasks and pilot goals gathered through the task ID questionnaire (see D3.1) to produce an engagement roadmap.

For the second iteration of the engagement roadmap, rather than combining a top-down timeline with bottom-up information gathered through questionnaires, the top-down timeline created with the project and technical leaders were discussed and developed with work package and task leaders to develop an updated engagement roadmap. Table 3 displays the second iteration of the engagement roadmap. Within Table 3, the white rows represent engagements related to the ACCEPT services development, blue rows represent pilot orientated engagements that are consistent across all pilot sites and the green rows represent pilot site activities that are unique to a specific pilot site. The main difference between the first and second iterations with the engagement roadmap is that the whole roadmap is now presented in a single table, with colors representing the responsibilities of different actors. The pilot specific activities are presented on a slightly more general level, yet this second iteration demonstrates better how different level activities fit together and construct a single engagement roadmap.

Table 3. Engagement roadmap (second iteration)

Timeline	Stakeholders	Description	Activity	Related tasks
M6	External & internal	Collection of market actor and prosumer requirements	Concept test survey	T2.1
M6-14	External & internal	Pilot welcome workshops/ACCEPT introduction event	Workshops	T3.1, T7.1, T3.4
M10	Internal	Feedback per pilot site on Business Cases-Use Cases-System Architecture and Measurement & Verification Methodology	Survey	T2.2, T2.3
M13	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	Variable One page newsletter per pilot	T3.1
M12-42	External	Project results shareback with all interested stakeholders	Communication/ dissemination	T3.4, T9.1

M12-15	External & internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	Survey	T2.5
M12-42	External	[SWISS pilot] – Continued communication with municipality for coordination purposes	Consultations and communication	T3.4
M10-13	External & internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	Audit	T6.1
M11-12	External	ACCEPT introduction for community members	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1, T7.1
M13-14*	External	ACCEPT persona validation workshop	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T3.1, T3.4
M15-16*	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M15-20	Internal	[SPANISH pilot] – consultation with AEM to investigate DSO perspective	Interview	T3.4
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation results	TBD	T6.4
M20-24 M15-M23	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	TBD	T6.5, T6.6
M26-27*	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 2: Feedback on ACCEPT system 2 nd prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8
M28-M30	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 2 nd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M35-36	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 3: Feedback on ACCEPT system final prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP7, WP8
M37-M39	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 3 rd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M27-M33	External & internal	Feedback on obstacles for DR application in energy communities	TBD	T8.1
M37-40	External	Feedback on business models	TBD	T8.4
M37-M42	External & internal	Sharing of ACCEPT results with businesses	TBD	T3.4

M37-42	External	[GREEK pilot] – consultation with DSO to discuss future services	Interview	T3.4
M37-42	External	[DUTCH pilot] – direct engagement with Grid operator to present the project and discuss any legal concerns	Interview	T3.4
M37-M42	External	Feedback on exploitable results & business potential	TBD	T8.2

*The date given for the workshops on persona validation and co-creation are likely to vary between pilot sites due to local needs (e.g. holiday periods may block certain time periods for scheduling engagements). This date should only be considered approximate

To complement the engagement planning process, monthly LL meetings have taken place which serves to monitor the progress of activities outlined in the engagement roadmap. Regular monthly meetings also allow the LL process to remain flexible regarding the planning of engagements. Flexibility is important for accommodating modifications to existing engagements or identifying new engagements that may be required. The LL monthly meetings have a representative from all WPs and pilot sites as well as technical and project coordinators.

2.2. Evaluation of the LL methodology

The hybrid approach utilized in the LL process thus far has proven to be effective in not only the planning of required engagements but also monitoring and updating the engagement roadmap. For example, the inclusion of the results share back activity planned for M13 was not initially foreseen in the first iteration of the engagement roadmap in M3. However, through discussions related to the concept survey undertaken as part of WP2 which took place in the LL monthly meetings, it was determined that sharing the results from the survey with the community would serve to build trust and a collaborative relationship.

One minor issue with the hybrid methodology that was identified was the process of combining the information from the top-down timeline with information from the task ID questionnaires to produce an engagement roadmap. Deriving an engagement roadmap from two different information sources caused confusion with regard to understanding and coordination. More specifically, the top-down and bottom-up explanation of the same task resulted in multiple tasks being created that essentially served the same purpose. To remedy this, the two perspectives (top-down and bottom-up) were aligned through one document. In the second iteration of the engagement roadmap, perspectives were gathered sequentially through the top-down timeline. The top-down timeline was discussed, reviewed and modified with WP and pilot leaders. This simplification improved the understanding at the coordination level and the efficiency of engagement planning.

3. Engagement activities M1-12

The engagement activities planned for the first year of the project can be considered in two channels, (1) Services and Solutions and (2) Pilot site activities. The engagements related to the services and solutions in the ACCEPT project cover the technical developments and business model design. The engagements under the scope of pilot site activities refer to activities related to the goals, context and key stakeholders in each pilot location. The pilot objectives are inevitably in the scope of ACCEPT and relate to the services and solutions, however, the various pilot regions are unique with individual goals, contexts, barriers and opportunities which may require targeted engagement activities.

Within this chapter, for both channels of engagements, an overview of the planned engagements and their current status will be presented. The completed and ongoing engagement activities will then be explained in the context of the LL process. Finally, an evaluation and next steps will be provided.

3.1. Services and Solutions

3.1.1. Overview of planned activities

Table 5 displays the planned engagements related to the ACCEPT solutions and services identified in M3 and their status at M12 of the project. Table 4 was constructed from the top-down timeline and bottom-up inputs described in D3.1.

Table 4. Services and Solutions: Planned engagements M1-12

Planned date	Stakeholder	Feedback required	WP(s) involved	Status
M6	External and internal	Collection of feedback on ACCEPT services from market actors' and prosumers'	WP2 (T2.1)	Completed
M10-13	External and Internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	WP6 (T6.1)	Ongoing
M12-15	External and internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	WP2 (T2.5)	Ongoing

3.1.2. Completed/ongoing activities

The goal of this section is not to explain the results and outcomes of the tasks which held engagements. Instead, the goal is to provide details on the engagement activity and the impact of the feedback gathering on the ACCEPT project.

3.1.2.1. Prosumer and citizen feedback on ACCEPT services (WP2)

The activities in WP2 aimed to gather early-stage feedback on the use cases (UC) and business cases (BC). Feedback on the UCs and BCs was gathered through the 'concept survey' questionnaires (see D2.1 for more info) issued to both citizens and prosumers as well as business and energy sector stakeholders. These questionnaires were issued to pilot area stakeholders and citizens by the pilot representatives in the ACCEPT consortium. The number of stakeholders reached via the questionnaires is displayed in Table 6.

Table 5. Summary of the number of responses to the concept survey

Pilot	Number of responses to concept survey
Greece	39
Spain	44
Switzerland	28
Netherlands	22
TOTAL	133

As the goal was to gather feedback on the UCs and BCs, a necessary step was to present these concepts in an understandable manner to stakeholders. Therefore, the technical descriptions of the UCs were ‘translated’ into what can be defined as a citizen service through collaboration between WP2 and WP3. Table 7 shows these service descriptions that were utilized in the concept survey. It is important to highlight this aspect in the context of the LLs as this translation process embodies the important element of bringing the community closer to the goals ACCEPT.

Table 6. Use Case Layperson Translation

Use Case	Technical description	Service description
UC1	Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings	Energy Consumption App What it does: Uses sensors to monitor near real-time energy consumption data from community buildings and homes. This data will be displayed via efficient and meaningful visualizations designed to give end-users a deeper insight and understanding of their energy consumption. The result: Through an app, you can see your energy consumption profile and patterns visualized intuitively, so that you can make more informed decisions about your energy consumption.
UC2 / UC13	Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimisation / Increase self-consumption at local community level	Optimization of heating and cooling devices What it does: This service will automatically utilize the most energy efficient settings so that traditionally heavy energy consumers – heating and cooling devices – can be optimized without sacrificing your comfort levels. The result: This allows the community to use more local, self-generated green energy (i.e. produced via renewable resources). As a result, your community will reduce its dependence on the main grid. Additionally, the optimization of heating and cooling devices may help you lower your bills.
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimisation taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements	Are you flexible with your energy consumption? What it does: Identifies building occupant’s (e.g. residents, businesses) energy consumption behavior and preferences. For example, preferred comfort levels (e.g. room temperature), daily activity patterns (e.g. working from home, cooking, relaxing). As a result our energy provider can provide energy at a lower price at certain hours. The result: By understanding when you, the energy consumer, might be more flexible in terms of energy consumption, the energy provider can better forecast and optimize energy distribution.
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	Can [Aspra Spitia] as a whole influence the price of electricity?

	and analysis in community level	<p>What it does: Combines individual user behaviors profiles into one larger profile for the community as a whole. Having one aggregate community profile helps to identify the optimal amount of energy to be purchased from the energy market.</p> <p>The result: Throughout the day, energy price varies based on the overall demand for energy. For example, in the evening, when most customers at home are cooking dinner and relaxing, energy prices will be higher. By better understanding your community's energy needs, it becomes easier for energy providers to purchase the optimal amount of energy from the energy market in total. This, in turn, allows energy providers to offer you 'dynamic pricing schemes' that reward customers with lower prices for not using energy at the costliest times of production.</p>
UC5	Intra-day district-level DR flexibility management for community self-balancing	<p>Energy generation forecasting</p> <p>What it does: Forecasts your community's renewable energy generation for the next hour or day ahead.</p> <p>The result: By predicting energy generation at the community level, more flexibility can be created, resulting in a more efficient and reliable energy network.</p>
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting	<p>Electric vehicle charging stations</p> <p>What it does: While your electric vehicle (EV)'s is charging, these charging stations may use your EV's battery to help with storing energy from the grid, depending on flexibility needs. For example, if extra storage is needed for the grid while you are charging your EV during the day, your car's battery will be used to help store surplus energy. These stations will forecast when and how EV users are charging in the energy community to decide when the EV's battery will be used as a battery for the grid. Calculates and forecasts electric vehicle charging flexibility for prosumers (energy customers that also produce some of their own energy from, for example, solar PV panels).</p> <p>The result: These charging stations will help to increase flexibility in the grid, which means reliable service and increased use of renewable energy. In exchange for using your battery, you may be offered lower prices for charging your vehicle.</p>
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility/ energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy	N/A – not B2C
UC8 / UC9	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes / Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	<p>Participation in a "Demand-Response" Scheme</p> <p>What it does: Invites 'prosumers' (energy customers that also produce some of their own energy from, for example, solar PV panels) to participate in 'Demand response schemes'. These schemes provide an opportunity for prosumers to play a significant role in the operation of the electric grid by reducing or shifting their electricity usage during peak, high demand periods.</p> <p>The result: Participants of prosumers in demand response schedules help to take the strain off of the grid and ensure everyone can enjoy a stable energy supply without fear of interruption.</p>
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service	<p>Monitoring tool for grid stability</p> <p>What it does: Provides a tool to monitor and control district level.</p> <p>The result: Provides the real-time status of the electrical network forecasts congestion events (black-outs, voltage problems, etc...) in order to prevent them or identify and evaluate the sections of the grid that could present congestion and act accordingly to avoid it.</p>

UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing	<p>App for Daily ahead Energy Cost What it does: Through an app, you receive information about the energy day head prices. The result: Provides you with a daily view of when energy prices will be best, so you can make more informed energy consumption decisions to help you save money.</p>
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DR management	<p>Optimal heating schedules What it does: At the community level, identifies the optimal schedules for operating heating systems. The result: This keeps your heat production at the optimal level, meaning you can maintain your comfort levels without compromising energy efficiency.</p>

3.1.2.2. Feedback on business models and Service Level Agreement contracts (WP2)

At this stage, internal work within work package 2 has been carried out towards defining the business models and market actor roles as well as assessing the types, structures, key components of SLA contracts (reported in D2.7). With regards to the related engagement activities, potential business models and SLAs defined through WP2 will be evaluated through the LL process. Feedback will be gathered from market actors in the pilot regions to validate the proposed business models and SLA contracts. External feedback is expected to take place in M15. Therefore, planning will begin in M13 in terms of identifying relevant stakeholders to engage with and preparing materials for an appropriate engagement methodology (e.g. interview, questionnaire, workshop, etc.).

3.1.2.3. Ex-ante pilot survey (WP6)

The ex-ante pilot surveys conducted in WP6 are aimed at identifying and assessing potential pilot participants in each region. The assessment was carried out through ex-ante audits which required the engagement of external stakeholders at pilot sites for recruitment purposes. The recruitment methodologies included workshops and events in each pilot region (explained further in section 3.2 of this document) which resulted in many external stakeholders showing interest and a desire to be part of ACCEPT. The number of stakeholders reached in each pilot for the first assessment phase in T6.1 is displayed in Table 8 (the first assessment phase refers to high-level selections from the technical coordination team, a final selection will take place in the second assessment phase of T6.1).

Table 7. Summary of the number of responses to the ex-ante survey

	<i>Ex-ante survey responses (WP6)</i>
Greece	61
Spain	55
Switzerland	64
Netherlands	40
TOTAL	220

3.1.3. Evaluation and next steps

To summarize, the engagements conducted related to the ACCEPT services and solutions have progressed well in the first 12 months of the project. The engagements undertaken as part of WP2 aimed at generating feedback from relevant market actors and prosumers on the UCs and BCs has been completed (see D2.1 for more details on the results of these tasks). The internal engagement work for the design of the business models and SLA contracts has begun, with external engagements on schedule (planned for M15).

With regards to the next steps, the upcoming engagements related to the services and solutions are displayed in Table 9. In addition to the aforementioned external stakeholder engagements concerning the business model and SLA contract development, the activities will continue in T6.1 of WP6 related to the ex-ante surveys and pilot participant selection. Following these continued activities, the primary focus of the engagements in the services and solutions stream will be the workshops aimed at gathering feedback on the ACCEPT prototypes deployed in the testbeds. Towards the end of the second year, the initial work prior to the pilot site deployment will begin, including installation and training for pilot participants.

Table 8. Services and Solutions engagement activities M13-24

M10-13	External & internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	Audit	T6.1
M13	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	Variable One page newsletter per pilot	T3.1
M15-16	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	TBD	T7.1
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation results	TBD	T6.4
M20-24 M15-M23	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	TBD	T6.5, T6.6

3.2. Pilot site engagement activities

3.2.1. Overview of planned activities

Table 9 displays the planned engagement activities related to the pilot sites identified in M3 and their status at M12 of the project. Table 9 was constructed from the top-down timeline and bottom-up inputs described in D3.1.

Table 9. Pilot site engagement activities: M1-M12

Planned date	Stakeholder	Feedback required	WP(s) involved	Status
M3-4	Internal	Selection of moderators for each pilot site country by GECCO	WP3	Delayed
M5	External	1 st site visits to pilot locations	WP3 (T3.4)	Ongoing*
M8-12	External	ACCEPT introduction for community members	WP2, WP3, WP6, WP7, WP9	Ongoing

*Although the 1st pilot site visits have not yet taken place physically (due to Covid-19 restrictions), remote-based work has been undertaken (explained in section 4.2) and site visits are planned for the first half of 2022.

3.2.2. Completed activities

3.2.2.1. (Remote) Site visit for pilots

Due to the restrictions caused by Covid-19, the first site visits to the pilot locations, and consequently the selection of moderators, planned within the first 6 months of the project was postponed. However, although physical travel and face-to-face engagements were not possible, the information from the site visits was obtained through remote work such as questionnaires, interviews and workshops with the pilot site representatives within the consortium.

The key information gathered remotely included determining the key stakeholders and details regarding why they are important, how to reach key stakeholders, identifying the contextual considerations at the regional level from the perspective of the pilot partners and understanding the primary goals of the pilot partners and their organizations in the context of ACCEPT. A summary of the findings for the remote pilot work is shown in Table 11 (for more details on the information gathered through the remote work see D3.7).

Table 10. Remote pilot work

	Interactions	Goals identified	Key SHs identified & mapped
Greece	All pilots filled out a scoping questionnaire, took part in an individual interview and a workshop for mapping key stakeholders	3	6
Spain		4	7
Switzerland		4	8
Netherlands		3	7

3.2.2.2. Introduction to community members

Several engagement activities were carried out at the pilot locations which at a high level served to introduce ACCEPT to the community. The activities carried out, such as workshops, interviews and presentations also actively engaged key community members and citizens which promotes the energy community ideals in ACCEPT. The activities undertaken are displayed in Table 12 (for more information on these activities see D3.5 and D3.7). These engagement activities and events also served the purpose of recruitment and feedback gathering for the tasks within WP2 and WP6 explained in section 3.1).

Table 11. Pilot site engagement activities

	<i>Engagement activities</i>
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop consisting of introductory presentation and open discussion • Questionnaires
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual interviews, phone calls and email correspondence • Video telco with Q&A session • Questionnaires
Switzerland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information letter for awareness-raising • One-to-one meetings • 2 workshops for recruiting and gauging interest in community
Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication outreach through a leaflet and an article in a local magazine • Individual one-to-one telephone calls

3.2.3. Evaluation and next steps

Through the remote work, a good understanding of the pilot locations has been developed. This understanding encompasses contextual needs, pilot goals and key pilot area stakeholders. This information will be invaluable as the ACCEPT project and demonstration activities progress. Several engagements have taken place at all pilot locations which has served the needs of tasks in WPs 2 and 6 and also served to raise community awareness and participation in the ACCEPT project. The main deviation from the initial timeline is the activities related to planning and executing initial pilot site visits. This delay was due to the Covid-19 pandemic which affected the ability to travel to pilot locations. To address this situation, although WP3 leaders were not able to physically travel to the pilot locations, information on key stakeholders, pilot goals and potential barriers was obtained remotely through multiple interviews and workshops. Despite the efforts to mitigate the impact of Covid-19, the value gained from in-person meetings with pilot leaders and physical engagements with key stakeholders should not be underestimated. Therefore, to complement the remote work undertaken thus far, plans are currently in place for the WP3 team to visit the pilot sites in M14-15.

Since the first engagement activities were conducted remotely and with adjusted programme, the first activity, "selection of moderators for each pilot site country by GECO" was not undertaken at the beginning of the project but was postponed to a moment presentational workshops can be conducted or moderators will be required to conduct online workshops, thus most likely in M14-M18.

For the future planned pilot engagements, Table 12 shows the activities that are scheduled to take place in the period of M13-24. In this period, several pilot-specific engagement activities have been planned (displayed in green). These pilot-specific activities are a direct result of the remote work undertaken as part of WP3. The remote work allowed for the identification of necessary interactions to engage with key stakeholders that will facilitate and optimize the success of the ACCEPT solutions. Another important engagement activity planned for M13 is the results 'share back'. The importance of this engagement resides in its objective to promote transparency of results gathered in ACCEPT (in this case, the feedback on the ACCEPT services gathered from community members) and build trust and a collaborative relationship with pilot communities.

As shown in Table 13, the engagements in M13-24 are geared towards interacting with key stakeholders at various pilot sites and conducting workshops which will allow for the co-creation of the first ACCEPT prototype. In addition, more workshops are planned at the pilot sites aimed at the validation of the customer personas developed as part of WP7 (See D7.1 for more information on how personas are developed and validated).

Table 12. Pilot site engagement activities: M13-24

M13	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	Variable One page newsletter per pilot	T3.1
M14-15	External	ACCEPT persona validation workshop and postponed 1 st pilot site visit.	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T3.1, T3.4
M15-16	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M15-20	Internal	[SPANISH pilot] – consultation with AEM to investigate DSO perspective	Interview	T3.4
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M20-24 M15-M23	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	TBD	T6.5, T6.6

4. Conclusion and next steps

Several successful engagements have been carried out as part of the LL process for both the services and solutions (section 3.1) and the pilot site engagement activities (section 3.2). For the services and solutions, engagements related to early concept testing of the BC and UCs have been completed, with feedback gathered from many various SHs. In addition, the ex-ante services aimed at recruiting pilot participants have completed the first stage of assessment. With regards to the pilot site engagements, activities that introduced ACCEPT to the community and raised awareness (as well as facilitated the tasks related to the services and solutions) have been carried out at all pilot sites. Despite the inability to conduct a site visit due to restrictions related to Covid-19, remote-based work was conducted with the pilot site representatives which ensured that vital information regarding contextual needs, pilot site goals and key stakeholders, normally collected through pilot site visits, was not missed.

The progress and success of the LL activities also need to be placed in the context of the project KPIs. Table 14 shows the quantified KPIs and their status at M12.

Table 13. Living Lab related KPIs

KPI	M12 status
1000 stakeholders participating in the co-creation process	133
More than 770 citizens actively engaged in validation activities	220
NPS >75% among pilot participants	-
Citizen satisfaction from ACCEPT solution >75%	-
Conscious acceptance of ACCEPT solution >90%	-
10 practices on energy community creation document	1

The First two KPIs listed in Table 13 relate to the number of stakeholders reached for co-creation and validation activities. Through the activities in WP2 and WP6, in collaboration with WP3 and WP7, significant progress has been made towards both these stakeholder outreach related KPIs. To build on the progress achieved thus far, the engagements planned in M13-24 will result in many further interactions with stakeholders in areas such as APP testing, persona validation and business model development. With the prototype testing expected to take place in the second year of the project, and further testing of later versions released after M24, more citizens will be actively engaged in the validation and co-creation process that will result in meeting the target KPIs listed in Table 13.

With regards to the net promoter score (NPS), satisfaction and acceptance level KPIs, the success of these targets will be determined in the latter phases of the project following full deployment in the pilot locations. However, what is important to consider at this stage is how these quantified targets are defined, and potentially achieved, from the various perspectives within the consortium, project coordinators, technical coordinators, pilot leaders, etc. It will also be important to consider what measures or methodologies are appropriate to determine satisfaction and acceptance.

Finally, with regards to the energy community creation document KPI of 10 best practices, at this stage, we can define one best practice (see Table 15). Following the work conducted in the first year of the project, it is clear that there is a necessity for implementing a LL process that allows for clear assessment and subsequent planning of engagements that will be key to creating an energy community in relation to renewable energy innovations and projects. When introducing new technologies or initiatives, it is essential to understand the local context in terms of its community objectives and the perspective of the stakeholders. It is also essential to promote inclusivity and transparency with regards to the new technologies and their purpose. The practical evidence that demonstrates the need for understanding the community and its stakeholders is reflected in the hybrid approach and site visits conducted as part of the LL process in ACCEPT.

Table 14. Table of best practices for energy community creation

Best practices on energy community creation
1. Understanding the community and stakeholders

The 10 best practices that will be defined in the ACCEPT project should be considered a working document until the final version of the LL report. The practices defined here may be altered, removed or added to as the project progresses and learnings are gained. The flexibility of these practices is not only practical but essential. The dynamic and investigative nature of a research project requires constant assessment and reflection on the methodologies implemented. Any methodologies or practices should be implemented as part of an iterative process that allows them to be evaluated and improved.